

Momentum and Wavelength in Quantum Bound States

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Early experiments linked to bound state quantum mechanics noticed discrete energy E levels. (Ignoring the issue of radiation from accelerating charges), classical physics predicts continuous E levels. If one tries a statistical approach i.e. thinks in terms of a “perceived” density $dt=C dx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity, one again has continuous energy levels. Thus, experimental results may suggest a non-classical condition which affects both acceptable densities and energy levels. Bypassing Newtonian mechanics which traces a particle through $x(t)$, we note that even classically a potential interacts with p and not v i.e. $pp/2m - p_0p_0/2m = -V(x)+V(x_0)$. This equation holds for $p= m_0 v = (.5m_0) 2v$ etc. Thus, energy flow i.e. p is of interest and if one does not trace the particle as $x(t)$ or consider acceleration (which is not considered statistically), one may view energy flux p as being “spread” over the x axis, it seems.

The length $1/p$ then corresponds to one unit of energy flux for the case of p . In other words, each p is associated with a length $1/p$. If this length may be physically resolved, one immediate trial result suggests a spatial probability which varies over $1/p$. In other words one may have a periodic function such as $\cos(px)$. This physical scenario seems to arise only when the quantum particle interacts with a potential. Calling $2\pi h/p = \text{wavelength}$, this length is not associated with the velocity of the particle, but with energy flow. Each particle has an identical type of cycling within its own wavelength i.e. $\cos(px)$ behaviour as each wavelength represents one unit of energy flux. The wavelength limits resolution and leads to a probability scheme. In a bound quantum system dx associated with $V(x)$ is usually much smaller than the larger wavelengths and so classical ideas such as p and $pp/2m$ still apply, but are modified i.e. multiplied by probabilities which may be positive or negative.

Having a spatial probability linked to density which also creates a probability scheme used to calculate average kinetic energy at each x based on $1/p$ type wavelengths is independent of classical physics. Trying to force average kinetic energy at x in the wavelength scheme to match $KE(x)$ classical leads to discrete E values.

Classical Physics

Newton’s laws allow one to track $x(t)$ i.e. one knows the position, velocity and acceleration of a particle at each t . This implies perfect resolution at all x points. Momentum and not velocity seems to be a key feature i.e. $dp/dt = F$, so momentum is considered as the important variable in this note. Momentum represents energy flux and does not track the motion of the particle. For example, $p= m_0 v = (.5m_0) 2v$ and both have the same momentum, but move at different speeds and are different places at different times. The equation:

$$pp/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

does not worry about what time a particle is at x or x_1 . It only links potential energy in x and $pp/2m$.

Newton's laws allow for continuous energy values E in ((1)). One may also view this equation in terms of spatial density i.e. a perceived density $dt = C dx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. Using a density makes the problem seem statistical with time removed, but all E values are again allowed.

It was noticed experimentally in the past, that discrete energy levels seemed to exist in electron states in atoms. This seems to possibly suggest discrete allowed densities. It seems that there may be an independent physical feature leading to these discrete energy and density levels. One may, however, wish to keep Newtonian ideas such as $pp/2m$ and p and treat the problem statistically somehow such that:

$$\text{KE average } (x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

New features must then enter through KE average (x) .

Quantum Bound States

If one does track acceleration, it seems that one may be applying a statistical approach as in classical statistical mechanics where one has a spatial density and a potential, (but does follow particles as they accelerate). Thus, one may suggest that $V(x)$ delivers stochastic hits, but that may also be viewed as classical if one uses:

$$\text{KE average } (x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p,x) \quad pp/2m \quad \text{where } a(p)>0 \text{ and } \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) = 1 \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, $a(p,x)$ suggests that a p is more likely to be found at one x than at another. $\exp(ipx)$ is an example of a function which would make each p be invariant in space, but it is complex and its real and imaginary parts may be positive and negative.

If one does follow a particle in time or use acceleration, then energy flow p is also not considered at a point. As a result, it seems that it must be spread out over the x range of the bound state. In such a case, a spatial length $1/p$ corresponds to one unit of energy flux. Thus, each p has its own unique $1/p$ length. This length could be created in succession if the particle were interacting with a potential. If the length may be physically resolved, one might suggest a spatial probability accounting for this resolution. Now, $\exp(ipx)$ mentioned above seems to make more sense. Its real part $\cos(px)$ has the same values within each $2\pi/p$ length and so different p 's undergo a very similar cycling in their own unique length interacting with $V(x)$. Positive and negative values may be associated with motion to the right or left and small values of $\cos(px)$ may be attributed to the particle, say moving fast within a tiny dx so its perceived presence is less than one just as in the classical perceived density $C dx/ v(x)$.

What is the resolution of $V(x)$ in such a situation? $V(x)$ is known at all points, i.e. has perfect resolution, so dx associated with $V(x)$ is smaller than the quantum wavelength, at least for the large wavelengths stirred up.

As a result of the physical resolution associated with the wavelength of the order $1/p$, a probability scheme arises. The kinetic energy is $pp/2m$ throughout a wavelength, but if the particle is perceived as being only partially present or moving in the opposite direction, $pp/2m$ is

modified by being multiplied by $\cos(px)$ (for example). Thus, various p_j $p_j/2m \cos(p_j x) a(p)$, where $a(p)$ is a weight, are added and then divided by a normalization function: $\sum_p a(p) \cos(px)$. Given that $V(x)$ represents complete resolution, $\exp(ipx)$ is like a lower resolution wave being stirred up in x space.

Given that the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ is 1 and is associated with a p , one may suggest that $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is the perceived spatial density of this new statistical system.

Consequences of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$

Given that each p i.e. energy flux is equivalent to $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ (or say $a(p)\cos(px)$ for positive parity), one can try to force a solution to:

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

It is not guaranteed, however, that there will be a solution for all E as in the classical case. In particular, ((3)) is a special type of eigenvalue differential equation which is already known to have discrete values of E for $W(x)$ which have certain boundary conditions, i.e. disappear as $x \rightarrow$ infinite.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that experiments on electron states in atoms which yield discrete energy differences, i.e. point to discrete energy levels, contradicts classical mechanics which allows for continuous values. We note that the perceived classical density $dt = C dx/v(x)$ ($v(x)$ =velocity) holds for all E as well. As a result, there may be a principle independent of classical physics which yields to discrete “density” functions and E values.

Classical physics follows a particle through $x(t)$ which yields continuous E values. A density, such as one which might appear in classical statistical mechanics $dt = C dx/v(x)$ also leads to continuous E . p , the energy flux, is classically the quantity of interest when dealing with a potential, not velocity. If p is not considered as being at specific points, then perhaps it is “smeared” over the entire x bound region. In such a case, $1/p$ represents the length associated with one unit of energy flux. Thus, each p has its own unique length $1/p$ which represents one unit. These units may be physically created through an interaction with $V(x)$ it seems. If such is the case, there should be a physical way to enforce the resolution i.e. a kind of “density” profile. If one considers the function $\exp(ipx)$, it has a modulus of 1 suggesting complete resolution everywhere, but if an interaction occurs, it may actually have less resolution as given by $\cos(px)$. The values of $\cos(px)$ are the same within each $1/p$ or more accurately $2\pi/3.14/p$ length. The values drop from one and also become negative. This may be associated with perceived probability i.e. a particle moving faster in one region may appear to be mostly absent from this region compared to a slower speed. Negative values may describe reversals in direction. Thus, $\cos(px) a(p)$, where $a(p)$ is a weight, becomes a kind of unnormalized probability. Newtonian ideas such as $p^2/2m$ still hold as the resolution of $V(x)$ is taken to be perfect i.e. it holds at every

x which is much higher resolution than $1/p$ regions. Thus, one may find average kinetic energy through:

$$KE(x) = \frac{[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)]}{[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)]}$$

Given that the idea of $\exp(ipx)$ does not follow from classical physics, the $KE(x)$ above, when added to $V(x)$ may only yield a constant E for discrete sets of $a(p)$, i.e. it may not be possible to find $a(p)$'s which hold for any E . Furthermore, $[\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)]$ times its conjugate gives perceived spatial density and should vanish as x goes to \pm infinite which also affects the possible solutions.

Thus, one has a kind of hybrid theory using Newtonian ideas such as p and $p^2/2m$, but combining them with a new probability $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ which does not exist in classical physics and is consequence of p , energy flux, being "smeared" over the x bound region such that $1/p$ represents a length with one unit of energy flux. This length has physical resolution and is a like a wave existing in x space which has perfect resolution due to $V(x)$ being defined at each x .

$\exp(ipx)$ is stirred up or manifested if the potential is of the order of the wavelength, e.g. if a two-slit setup is separated by about a wavelength. If the two slits are separated by a large distance and the slit width is also large, then classical results occur. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ may exhibit wave behaviour with some potentials (as in scattering scenarios), but particle behaviour for other potentials. As a result, it needs to carry both particle ($\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$) and wave $\cos(px)$ features.